

Studies on Some Monofluophosphates: Part IV. Pressure composition isothermal

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Pressure composition isothermal studies of both sulphate and monofluophosphate hydrates of Cd, Mn, Ni, Cr (III) and Fe (III) have been made. The different hydrates stable at the same temperature correspond to the same type of formulae in both cases which establishes beyond doubt the analogy between the two anions.

The compositions of the hydrates of monofluophosphates¹ and sulphates which are formed by the combination of two substances of widely different volatility—the very difficultly volatile metal salt and the readily volatile water—have been determined by investigating their isothermal decomposition (dehydration) from the standpoint of the laws of heterogeneous equilibrium. In this case we meet the phenomena of the two components and three phases system making the system univariant and to each temperature there will correspond a certain definite vapour pressure (dissociation pressure) which will be independent of the relative or absolute amount of the phases. Therefore, on dehydration of a salt hydrate at constant temperature by pumping off the water there will be a stepwise diminution of the vapour pressure indicating the formation of more than one definite dissociating compounds at that temperature. In case a hydrate does not dissociate into a second definite solid phase, the system becomes bivariant and can exist therefore at different values of temperature and pressure of vapour. There will therefore be no 'break' in the pressure-composition curve. This is known as zeolytic curve and shows that water which serves to improve the packing can be expelled from the crystal lattice without bringing about any change of structure.

In actual experiment it has been found that the change is not so sharp as expected. The classical dehydration mechanism in which sharp change from a hydrate to lower hydrate or anhydrous substance is assumed, probably holds only in the neighbourhood of the transition temperature. At lower temperature a different mechanism may be possible.² Under these conditions as water of crystallisation leaves the surface the residual skeleton lattice structure remains as a film held to the unchanged lattice by valence forces. As water continues to evaporate, this film becomes thicker and the outer portions become unstable. The instability finally causes rearrangement to the lattice of the other solid phase. As the lower hydrate or the anhydrous substance is formed, a skeleton lattice zone of constant (on the average) thickness precedes it into the crystals of the original hydrate except probably in the neighbourhood of the upper transition temperature. This constant thickness zone is the cause for the constancy of the vapour pressure during dehydration.

1. Singh, E. B. and Sinha, P. C., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 407, and 411.

2. Duerall, V. R. and Tower, C. F., *Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1935, 12, 143-152.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used is principally the same as was used by Sinha and Ray³ with slight modification and improvement. The experiment consisted essentially in the determination of the loss of weight of water as it was gradually removed at a fixed temperature and recording the equilibrium pressure exerted. Approximately 0.5 to 1 gm. of the freshly crystallised salt hydrate was used with a little of conductivity water. The equilibrium pressure was reached after leaving it for a few days. A series of values of pressure and weights corresponding to each pressure were thus obtained. When no further loss in the weight of the substance was observed, the substance was quantitatively taken out and analysed. From the results number of molecules of water lost and number of water molecules that remained per mol. of the anhydrous salt at each stage were calculated. The results are represented graphically by plotting pressures against number of water molecules.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE I
CADMIUM MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

Weight of anhydrous salt 1.4840 gm.		Weight of water 0.1232 gm.		Temp. 50.25°C.
Pressure in mm. of Hg.	Weight in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.		No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt.
93.0	2.1198	0.6358		5.0094
93.0	1.8920	0.4080		3.2108
93.0	1.8590	0.3750		2.9510
93.0	1.8302	0.3462		2.7244
17.05	1.8186	0.3346		2.6931
17.05	1.8172	0.3332		2.622
17.05	1.7956	0.3116		2.452
17.05	1.7805	0.2965		2.393
17.05	1.7542	0.2702		2.126
17.05	1.7394	0.2554		2.0098
17.05	1.7224	0.2384		1.876
17.05	1.6723	0.1883		1.482
17.05	1.6273	0.1433		1.1277
17.05	1.6120	0.1280		1.0073
2.2	1.6118	0.1278		1.0057
2.2	1.6104	0.1264		0.9947
2.2	1.6072	0.1232		0.9687

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TABLE II

MANGANESE MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt 1.6655 gm.</i>		<i>Wt. of water 0.1902 gm.</i>		<i>Temp. 50.0°C.</i>	
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mols. per mol. of anhy- drous salt.		
92.5	3.0328	1.3673			
92.5	2.4280	0.7625	6.968		
92.5	2.2223	0.5568	3.886		
92.5	2.0813	0.4158	2.838		
56.85	2.0743	0.4088	2.119		
11.9	2.0501	0.3846	2.083		
11.9	2.0221	0.3566	1.960		
11.9	1.9628	0.2973	1.817		
11.9	1.9335	0.2680	1.515		
11.9	1.9181	0.2526	1.366		
11.9	1.9114	0.2459	1.287		
11.9	1.8893	0.2238	1.253		
5.1	1.8702	0.2047	1.140		
1.45	1.8635	0.1980	1.043		
1.45	1.8607	0.1952	1.009		
1.45	1.8557	0.1902	0.995		
			0.969		

TABLE III

NICKEL MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt 0.4753 gm.</i>		<i>Wt. of water 0.2851 gm.</i>		<i>Temp. 29.8°C.</i>	
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhy- drous salt.		
30.1	0.9702	0.4949	9.053		
30.1	0.9541	0.4788	8.758		
30.1	0.9383	0.4630	8.470		
30.1	0.9304	0.4551	8.326		
30.1	0.9062	0.4309	7.883		
30.1	0.8822	0.4069	7.444		
30.1	0.8696	0.3943	7.213		
30.1	0.8445	0.3692	6.751		
30.1	0.8320	0.3567	6.525		
30.1	0.8264	0.3511	6.422		
30.1	0.8169	0.3416	6.250		
30.1	0.8049	0.3296	6.030		
2.42	0.7903	0.3150	5.762		
2.42	0.7824	0.3071	5.615		
2.42	0.7671	0.2918	5.398		
2.42	0.7629	0.2876	5.261		
2.42	0.7609	0.2859	5.224		
2.42	0.7604	0.2851	5.216*		

TABLE IV
CHROMIUM(III) MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 0.8674 gm.		<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.2299 gm.		<i>Temp.</i> 50.0°C.
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt.	
92.5	1.8073	0.9399	23.935	
92.5	1.7156	0.8482	21.600	
92.5	1.6425	0.7751	19.740	
92.5	1.6013	0.7339	18.690	
73.01	1.5713	0.7039	17.925	
73.01	1.5587	0.6919	17.605	
73.01	1.5375	0.6701	17.065	
73.01	1.5150	0.6476	16.492	
73.01	1.4925	0.6251	15.920	
73.01	1.4788	0.6114	15.570	
73.01	1.4574	0.5900	15.025	
72.0	1.4336	0.5662	14.420	
65.8	1.3641	0.4967	12.650	
60.0	1.3245	0.4571	11.640	
52.0	1.2897	0.4223	10.755	
36.20	1.2531	0.3857	9.823	
25.54	1.2290	0.3616	9.209	
18.0	1.2099	0.3425	8.723	
13.6	1.1947	0.3273	8.336	
10.15	1.1829	0.3155	8.035	
5.05	1.1425	0.2751	7.007	
1.7	1.1076	0.2402	6.117	
1.7	1.0996	0.2322	5.914	
1.7	1.0973	0.2299	5.885	

TABLE V
IRON (III) MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 1.086 gm.		<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.1449 gm.		<i>Temp.</i> 50.25°C.
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt.	
93.0	1.9303	0.8443	17.51	
93.0	1.7483	0.6623	13.79	
93.0	1.7047	0.6187	12.83	
87.0	1.6638	0.5778	12.00	
80.5	1.6407	0.5547	11.5	
71.0	1.5781	0.4921	11.203	
65.05	1.5351	0.4491	9.311	
60.6	1.4885	0.4025	8.345	
54.21	1.4531	0.3671	7.611	
49.2	1.4207	0.3347	6.999	
44.0	1.3775	0.2915	6.044	
30.69	1.3375	0.2515	5.215	

TABLE V (contd.)

Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt,
19.50	1.9114	0.2254	4.567
18.20	1.298	0.2120	4.396
10.26	1.2870	0.2010	4.168
8.40	1.2835	0.1975	4.095
3.70	1.2515	0.1655	3.431
1.75	1.2339	0.1479	3.067
0.80	1.2310	0.1450	3.0046
0.80	1.2309	0.1449	3.0045

TABLE VI

CADMIUM SULPHATE
(Analytical Results)

	<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 2.4433 gm.	<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.2033 gm.	<i>Temp.</i> 50.25°C.
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhy- drous salt.
90.3	3.1446	0.7013	3.3205
90.3	3.0901	0.6468	3.0624
90.3	3.0395	0.5902	2.795
84.2	3.0254	0.5821	2.7561
81.95	3.0057	0.5624	2.6628
81.95	2.9816	0.5383	2.5487
81.95	2.9614	0.5181	2.453
81.95	2.9396	0.4963	2.3498
81.95	2.9205	0.4772	2.2594
81.95	2.9004	0.4571	2.1643
81.95	2.8655	0.4222	1.999
81.95	2.8101	0.3668	1.7367
81.95	2.7796	0.3363	1.5923
81.95	2.7639	0.3206	1.518
81.95	2.7241	0.2808	1.3296
81.95	2.6916	0.2489	1.1757
81.95	2.6732	0.2301	1.0895
81.95	2.6614	0.2181	1.0327
99.90	2.6544	0.2111	0.9993
12.40	2.6528	0.2095	0.9919
5.86	2.6527	0.2094	0.9915
2.95	2.6527	0.2094	0.9915
2.95	2.6472	0.2099	0.9654
2.95	2.6466	0.2093	0.9626
2.95	2.6466	0.2093	0.9626

TABLE VII
MANGANESE MONOFLUOPHOSPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 1.8440 gm.	<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.2054 gm.	<i>Temp.</i> 50.0°C.	
Pressure in mm. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhy- drous salt.
80.1	2.8677	1.0237	4.659
80.1	2.8341	0.9901	4.5009
80.1	2.7484	0.9044	4.111
80.1	2.6165	0.7725	3.511
80.1	2.5719	0.7279	3.3085
80.1	2.4098	0.5658	2.572
80.1	2.3917	0.4877	2.217
80.1	2.2615	0.4175	1.898
80.1	2.2096	0.3656	1.662
80.1	2.1002	0.2562	1.165
68.4	2.0711	0.2271	1.0332
48.27	2.0670	0.2230	1.013
24.20	2.0650	0.2210	1.0045
2.90	2.0638	0.2198	0.9991
2.90	2.0634	0.2194	0.9973
2.90	2.0631	0.2191	0.9734
2.90	2.0494	0.2054	0.9336

TABLE VIII
NICKEL SULPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 1.0165 gm.	<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.5925 gm.	<i>Temp.</i> 29°C.	
Pressure in mm. of Hg.	Weight in gm. of subs. in successive stages	Total wt. in gm. of water.	No. of water mol. per mol. of anhy- drous salt.
28.25	2.3816	1.3651	11.53
28.25	2.0118	0.9953	8.407
28.25	1.9228	0.9063	7.654
28.25	1.8946	0.8781	7.416
28.25	1.8686	0.8521	7.197
28.25	1.8526	0.8361	7.069
28.25	1.8316	0.8151	6.887
28.25	1.8105	0.8030	6.782
28.25	1.8014	0.7849	6.690
28.25	1.7730	0.7565	6.193
28.25	1.7496	0.7331	6.156
28.25	1.7454	0.7289	6.064
28.25	1.7345	0.7180	6.026
28.25	1.7298	0.7133	5.839
2.5	1.7095	0.6930	5.763
2.5	1.6988	0.6823	5.573
2.5	1.6764	0.6599	5.339
2.5	1.6487	0.6322	5.117
2.5	1.6222	0.6057	5.004
2.5	1.6090	0.5925	

TABLE IX
CHROMIUM(III) SULPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 2.674 gm.	<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.6308 gm.	<i>Temp.</i> 50.25°C.	
Pressure in m.m. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	
		No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt.	
93.0	5.1511	2.4771	20.17
93.0	4.9247	2.2507	18.324
60.9	4.8708	2.1968	17.89
60.9	4.8257	2.1517	17.52
60.9	4.7747	2.1007	17.102
60.9	4.7562	2.0822	16.952
60.9	4.7338	2.0598	16.77
60.9	4.6395	1.9655	16.002
60.9	4.5751	1.9011	15.477
60.9	4.5396	1.8596	15.14
54.1	4.4604	1.7864	14.544
53.05	4.4313	1.7579	14.306
47.5	4.3562	1.6822	13.695
41.8	4.2889	1.6149	13.147
37.01	4.2270	1.5530	12.643
32.5	4.1739	1.4999	12.21
29.5	4.0487	1.3747	11.192
16.0	3.9907	1.3167	10.72
10.7	3.9280	1.2540	10.21
7.8	3.8699	1.1959	9.796
5.05	3.7893	1.1153	9.08
3.0	3.6787	1.0047	8.18
2.51	3.5239	0.8499	6.919
2.40	3.4748	0.8008	6.52
2.0	3.4011	0.7271	5.92
2.0	3.3552	0.6812	5.546
2.0	3.3048	0.6308	5.136

TABLE X
IRON(III) SULPHATE
(Analytical Results)

<i>Wt. of anhydrous salt</i> 0.9237 gm.	<i>Wt. of water</i> 0.2228 gm.	<i>Temp.</i> 50°C.	
Pressure in mm. of Hg.	Wt. in gm. of subs. in successive stages.	Total wt. in gm. of water.	
		No. of water mol. per mol. of anhydrous salt.	
41.2	1.3846	0.4609	11.08
31.0	1.3779	0.4542	10.916
6.5	1.3702	0.4465	10.791
6.2	1.3691	0.4454	10.704
4.75	1.3667	0.4430	10.646
4.65	1.3644	0.4407	10.591
4.00	1.3363	0.4126	9.916
3.5	1.3072	0.3895	9.216
3.1	1.2761	0.3526	8.47
2.6	1.2623	0.3386	8.138
2.5	1.2412	0.3175	7.694
2.5	1.2153	0.2918	7.013
2.5	1.1465	0.2228	5.355

Cadmium monofluophosphate : The breaks in the isothermal correspond to two stable solid phases, $\text{CdPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CdPO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 50.25°C .

Manganese monofluophosphate : The break in the isothermal indicates the existence of two solid phases $\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 50°C . No break in the curve corresponding to the $\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been found. Probably the tetrahydrate is not stable at 50°C . Due to experimental difficulties it could not be possible to do the experiment below room temperature (35°C).

Nickel monofluophosphate : There is practically no difference between vapour pressure of $\text{NiPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that of water. Dehydration results in a sharp break in the curve showing the existence of next definite solid phase corresponding to $\text{NiPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Further dehydration could not be possible under the condition of the experiment.

Chromium monofluophosphate : In this case constant pressure is obtained between 18 and 15 molecules of water giving evidence of two definite hydrates; with further withdrawal of the water vapour there is a continuous change in the composition of the solid phase and diminution of the vapour pressure. The pressure again becomes constant after the composition of the solid phase corresponds to have 6 mols. of water. Therefore at 50°C . only three hydrates of Chromium (III) monofluophosphate are stable, viz., $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. As no break in the pressure composition curve has been observed between 15 and 6 molecules of water, it indicates the existence of no definite hydrate between them.

Iron monofluophosphate : From the very start there is continuous change in the composition of the solid phase with diminution of the vapour pressure. It is, therefore, clear that there does not exist any definite hydrate of iron (III) monofluophosphate at the temperature of the experiment.

Cadmium sulphate : The plot of pressures against number of water molecules shows break corresponding to two stable solid phases $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 50.25°C .

Manganese sulphate : Manganese sulphate dissolves in its water of crystallisation giving a saturated solution which exerts a pressure equal to 80.1 mm. of mercury. The vapour pressure remains constant until the last trace of liquid has evaporated. Further dehydration results in the formation of a stable solid phase corresponding to $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and the vapour pressure drops suddenly to 2.9 mm. of mercury. This suggests that $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is the only stable hydrate of manganese sulphate at 50°C .

Nickel sulphate : The vapour pressure of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is almost equal to that of the saturated solution and is slightly lower than that of water. The value of pressure obtained by us differs very little from those of the work of Lescoeur and of Schumb. Further dehydration results in the formation of the hexahydrate as next stable solid phase and the vapour pressure falls to 2.5 mm. of mercury. No change in the vapour pressure could be observed under this condition on further dehydration.

Chromium(III) sulphate : As in the case of chromium (III) monofluophosphate, in this case also constant pressure is exerted between 18 and 15 molecules of water giving favourable evidence of the existence of two stable solid phases. Further dehydration leads to a continuous change in the composition of the solid phases with diminution of the vapour

pressure. The pressure again becomes constant after the composition of the solid phase corresponds to have 6 mols. of water. This shows that three hydrates, viz., $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 18 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 15 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ are stable solid phases and the other hydrates so far reported are not definite compounds at least at 50°C .

Iron(III) sulphate: The isothermal graph shows no evidence of any stable solid phase. A continuous change in the composition of the solid phase with diminution of the vapour pressure has been observed. This suggests that no definite hydrate of ferric sulphate exists at 50°C .

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